

MECHANISM OF INNOVATIVE CAPACITY MANAGEMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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One of the most important directions is the correct formation of management in building innovative potential, introducing innovations and creating the necessary conditions for their development. The innovative potential of territories has its own characteristics, which include such as the identification of objects important for their development and the use of objective indicators representing levels of competitive advantage. Competitiveness is central to the assessment of innovation potential. Innovations, as well as innovative technologies that enhance competitiveness, are also becoming important.

The main purpose of managing the innovative potential of personnel is its optimization, i.e. the formation of an optimal innovative potential of personnel corresponding to the conditions of innovation implementation. The priority goal of the company's personnel policy is the formation of a highly qualified and motivated team capable of increasing competitiveness and strengthening the company's leading positions in the satellite market.

The social essence of enterprise personnel management depends on the social policy determined by the country.

It is necessary that employees of institutions of each enterprise take an active part in the implementation of social policy. Social policy in the economic system is expressed in two ways:

- firstly, the progress of economic growth is expressed in growth at the level of a particular country as national wealth, at the enterprise level as gross income. This wealth expresses the main purpose of economic activity in the organization of social conditions;
- social policy is the goal of economic development. Economic development ensures the implementation of social policy;
- secondly, social policy is the main factor of economic development.

Economic growth is expressed in the social conditions created by each enterprise for the work of service personnel. The higher the economic level of the enterprise, the higher the demand for the labor of service personnel. The social essence of the company's personnel management in this case provides

them with comprehensive intellectual development, qualified formation of highly qualified professionals and high-level specialists.

Representing the socio-economic development of a territory requires focusing on the role and place of innovation in comparing territories and overcoming economic fluctuations. As a result, the regions will be able to evaluate their innovation processes and identify specific, planned, value-based areas of their special attention and organize innovative activities based on them. One of the most important directions is the correct formation of management in building innovative potential, introducing innovations and creating the necessary conditions for their development.

When forming a mechanism for managing the innovative potential of workers in the textile industry in the context of modernization and digitalization of the economy, special attention should be paid to the system of their professional development and retraining (Fig.1).

The innovative activities of the enterprise expand in all the work of production and management with rain, the need arises for professional employees who can make decisions to ensure the production and delivery of innovative technologies specific. In the conditions of digitization of the economy, it serves to identify the necessary conditions for the development of the innovative potential of employees at enterprises and the implementation of an innovative strategy, identify the current conditions of the enterprise, improve the innovative potential and conditions for the implementation of innovative activities of employees based on existing resources, increase the competitiveness of employees.

Figure 1. Innovative capacity management model at the enterprise.

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The advantage of this approach is that it allows you to see the impact of the Personnel Management function on the overall management process of the enterprise. At the same time, it ensures the transition of functions from long-term, strategic applications to current, operational actions of the enterprise and contributes to the successful operation of the enterprise.

In the context of market economy relations, the formation of Personnel Management at the enterprise, its effective use depends on the level of organization and personal provision of their services to the extent that they correspond to the optimal market requirements in order to ensure the growth of labor productivity.

Based on the analysis of the factor PEST carried out as a result of several studies, as well as the analysis of the results of the survey conducted among executive employees within the selected enterprises in the textile industry, we believe that in the future it is advisable to carry out the following in the direction of developing the activity of the textile industry in:

- step-by-step development of infrastructure systems necessary for the development of the industry on the basis of factor analysis of the potential of enterprises of the textile industry;
- training qualified personnel for textile industry enterprises;
- effectively ensure the interaction of elements of the internal and external environment by coordinating management processes between enterprises;
- development of effective mechanisms for attracting investments to finance enterprises of the textile industry.

The future full-fledged implementation of the proposed priorities in the field will make it possible to develop the processes of organization and management of the activities of enterprises of the textile industry and to control and coordinate factors affecting the effectiveness of the activities, to reduce the level of possible risks.

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